

LOW COST COMPOSITE FABRICATION: VACUUM ASSISTED RESIN INFUSION

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SUMMARY: To explore an alternative to the conventional and expensive prepreg/autoclave process, this study was initiated to evaluate vacuum assisted resin infusion (VARI) process as a low-cost composite fabrication method. In this work, we studied the selection of materials suitable for liquid infusion process, the processing parameters necessary for parts fabrication, resin flow simulation, and composites' properties evaluation to gain a better understanding of the VARI process.

KEYWORDS: Low-cost Composite Fabrication, Vacuum Assisted Resin Infusion (VARI), Resinfusion™ 8607R/H, Corrugated Panel

1. INTRODUCTION

The high cost of manufacturing using the conventional prepreg/autoclave process has been a deterrent to the extensive use of composites. The disadvantages of prepreg/autoclave fabrication method include its high material and labor costs; high capital expenditure; and long processing time. To compete with metal part fabrication economically, low-cost composite fabrication (LCCF) techniques such as filament winding, VARI, RTM, SCRIMP and other liquid infusion process have evolved as alternatives to the prepreg/autoclave method. By making use of raw materials, the "semi-automated" LCCF techniques can be used to produce advanced composite components at significantly lower cost in production. This work evaluated VARI as a composite processing technique currently of interest to the marine and even aerospace industry for high performance composite parts.

2. VACUUM ASSISTED RESIN INFUSION

Vacuum assisted resin infusion (VARI) is one of the advanced liquid infusion techniques for forming high-quality composite. The process is similar to the well-known resin transfer molding (RTM) but utilizes only one tool half in combination with a vacuum bag. Resin is injected into the reinforcing fabric on the mold under vacuum through a high permeability layer (HPL) placed above the fabric. The vacuum helps provide for complete fabric wet-out and minimise void content. The VARI technique permits the use of raw fibers and resin systems and is proving to be one of the most cost effective manufacturing techniques among other liquid molding process e.g. RRIM, SRIM, SCRIMP, RTM. A schematic diagram of the VARI process is presented in Fig 1.

Resin Trap

Fig 1. Resin infusion process

3. OBJECTIVES

In this work, proof-of-concept parts were fabricated to verify if composites of fiber volume fraction (V_f) as high as 60% were possible and to evaluate what types of complex geometry part could be produced via the VARI process. The candidate parts were simple flat panels and complex corrugated panels of different lay-up and thickness configurations.

4. RESIN

4.1 Selection considerations

As pointed out by Start et al. ^[1], there are several requirements of a resin system to be used in liquid infusion process. These include its ease of processing, performance and compatibility. Of most importance is the ease of processing, which may be defined as the ease of use under the conditions specified by the process. These are usually low viscosity, long working time, and short cure time. The lower the temperature is required to achieve these characteristics, the better the resin system is generally accepted. Performance is dependent upon the end-use requirements for strength and stiffness. Compatibility is the suitability of the resin systems with the reinforcement materials utilized in the process to provide complete fabric wet-out and prevent undesired side reactions.

In the preliminary resin selection, a series of new epoxy resin systems specially formulated by resin suppliers for the production of composite parts via the infusion process were evaluated in terms of their ease of processing, performance and cost. Subsequently, we focused on the ResinfusionTM epoxies (products of Ciba Specialty Chemicals Corporation) that feature low viscosity needed for good wet-out of reinforcing materials using the infusion process. We finally selected ResinfusionTM 8607R/H resin; a two-components toughened epoxy resin system which offers desirable processing conditions, good dimensional stability and excellent cured physical characteristics.

Table 1: Neat resin properties of ResinfusionTM 8607, RTM6 & Fibredux 6376

Property	Resinfusion TM 8607R/H	RTM 6	Fibredux 6376
Hardness (Shore D)	86	-	-

Ultimate flexural strength (MPa)	93.5	-	144
Flexural modulus (GPa)	2.29	-	4.4
Ultimate tensile strength (MPa)	64.3	78	105
Tensile modulus (GPa)	2.58	3.2	3.6
Ultimate compressive strength (MPa)	228.8	-	-
Tg (°C)	173	-	-
Density (g/cc)	1.09	-	1.31

Table 2: Processing characteristics of Resinfusion™ 8607 R/H epoxy system

Mix Ratio, (% by weight)	100:35 (Resin:Hardener)
Color	Off-white
Viscosity, (cP)	
@ 25 °C	1,800
@ 49 °C	<300
Gel time, (mins)	
@ 25 °C	670
@ 49 °C	30-60
8607 R/H epoxy system is a product of Ciba Specialty Chemicals Viscosity = Ubbelohde tube viscometer Pot life = time required to double initial viscosity (Brookfield viscometer) Gel time = hot plate gel determination	

4.2 Resinfusion™ 8607 R/H

Start et al. [1] and Stockon [2] discuss the characterisation of high performance resin systems (DPL-862/RSC-763, COMPIMIDE 65 FWR) for RTM processing. In a similar methodology, the processing of Resinfusion™ 8607 R/H resin system for VARI is presented.

Resinfusion™ 8607 R/H is specially formulated for use in the production of advanced composites using VARI, RTM, SCRIMP or other liquid infusion process. Its low-mixed viscosity and wet-out potential greatly enhance the ease of processing. The resin is able to cure to self-support after 24 to 48 hours at ambient temperature. Composites produced using Resinfusion™ 8607 R/H resin system can achieve a T_g of 173°C following a post cure.

The processing characteristics of the Resinfusion™ 8607R/H system are shown in Table 2. It is apparent that the viscosity of the resin is an important factor in determining a desirable processing conditions. If the viscosity is too high, the resin will not flow easily and may not penetrate fiber bundles, giving poor wet out. If the viscosity is too low, the resin may follow a path of least resistance and leave voids or dry spots. As a rule of thumb, the resin viscosity is recommended to be in the range of 100cP to 500cP. For Resinfusion™ 8607R/H, the resin has an initial high viscosity of 1800cP at ambient temperature. However, the viscosity can be reduced to less than 300cP upon heating to 50°C while maintaining appreciable working time.

4.3 Determining of isothermal viscosity sweep

The isothermal viscosity sweeps at 50°C, 60°C and 70°C were established for Resinfusion™ 8607 R/H using the Brookfield rotating spindle viscometer. A resin viscosity of less than 500cP could readily be achieved by mixing the resin and hardener by a weight ratio of 100:35 at

these temperatures. From the isothermal viscosity profiles shown in Fig 2, the working time with viscosity of less than 500cP at 50°C is at least 30 minutes.

Fig 2. Isothermal viscosity sweeps of Resin

5. FIBER REINFORCEMENT

5.1 Selection Considerations

In the fiber reinforcement selection, we considered the six basic design variables: thickness, weight, yarn size, count, weave pattern and finish/sizing. In this work, the chosen choice of fiber reinforcement was Hexcel's standard modulus 3-K carbon fabrics with epoxy sizing, of Style 433, 5 harness satin weave, 285g/m² weight and 0.32mm ply thickness at 50% fiber volume fraction.

As noted in the Hexcel's Fabric Handbook, the weave pattern is an important factor in determining many of the performance factors of a fabric, including dimensional stability, drapability and formability, porosity and the fabric's wet-out characteristics, strength and modulus translation of the fibers in a laminate. For this study, we selected the satin pattern in which the fill and warp yarns do not interlace over and under at every yarn intersection, Instead, the yarns in both directions will "float" over several intersections before interlacing under one. Satin fabrics have a higher degree of drapability than plain weave fabrics and are well suited for manufacturing of the corrugated panel with complex shape profile.

5.2 Predictive calculation for fiber volume determination

The technical data of the carbon reinforcement: Style 433, 3K carbon fiber is presented in Table 3.

Table 3: Technical data of Hexcel Style 433, 3K carbon reinforcement

Style	Warp & Fill /Yarn	Weave	Count Yarns/inch	Weight G/m ² & Oz/yd ²		Weight Ratio	Thickness Laminate 50%	
				GSM	OSY		mils	mm
433	3K carbon	5 H.S.	18.0 x 18.0	285	8.4	50:50	12.6	0.32

The thickness listed for the carbon reinforcement is laminate thickness at 50% fiber volume; which is a calculated value. With this as a reference value, we will be able to determine the theoretical thickness for achieving 60% fiber volume in the making of composite parts.

We made use of equation (1).

$$v_f = \frac{(r_{Af})(n)}{(r_f)(H)} \quad (1)$$

where

V_f is the % fiber volume

ρ_f is the density of fiber fabric

ρ_{Af} is the area density of fiber fabric

n is the no. of plies

H is the laminate thickness

For $n = 1$, the laminate thickness, H will be the fabric thickness, h

We have
$$h = \frac{\mathbf{r}_{Af}}{(\mathbf{r}_f)(v_f)} \quad (2)$$

For $\rho_{Af} = 285 \text{ g/m}^2$ (or 0.285 kg/m^2), $h_1 = 0.32 \text{ mm}$ (or 0.00032 m)
at 50% V_f for Style 433 carbon fabric

We have
$$h_1 = \frac{\mathbf{r}_{Af}}{(\mathbf{r}_f)(50\% v_f)} = \frac{0.285}{(\mathbf{r}_f)(0.5)} = 0.00032 \text{ m}$$

$$\Rightarrow \mathbf{r}_f = \frac{(h_1)(50\% v_f)}{(\mathbf{r}_{Af})} = \frac{(0.285)}{(0.00032)(0.5)} = 1781.25 \text{ kg/m}^3$$

For $\rho_{Af} = 285 \text{ g/m}^2$, $V_f = 0.6$ or 60%

We have
$$h_2 = \frac{\mathbf{r}_{Af}}{(\mathbf{r}_f)(60\% v_f)} = \frac{285}{(1781250)(0.6)} \approx 0.000267 \text{ m}$$

Therefore, to achieve a high fiber volume fraction of more than 60%, the reduced ply thickness of the carbon reinforcement has to be less than 0.267mm.

5.3 Fabric compaction

A compaction test was carried out on 23 plies of dry carbon fabric using Instron's Universal Testing Machine as shown in Fig 3. The objective of the test was to determine the compaction pressure versus thickness response of the carbon fabric. The experimental result shows that a de-bulking pressure of about 230kPa is required to compact the 23 plies of dry carbon fabric to a thickness of about 6.09mm to attain more than 60% V_f . This pressure is deemed not

achievable under vacuum compaction.

Fig 3. Compaction pressure versus thickness response

In addition to the limitation of vacuum integrity, there is also a phenomenon of compaction loss during the stage of resin infusion in VARI. A research study on resin infusion process was carried out by the Center for Composite Materials (CCM), University of Delaware: In-situ monitoring of fabric compaction during infusion by a laser-based gantry system. The work found out that a compaction loss of up to 10% is possible during the resin infusion or wet-out stage, depending on the fiber reinforcement used.

Thus, the limitation of the vacuum integrity and compaction loss are two reasons why the fiber volume fraction of composite parts made using VARI is typically in the range of 40-55%, as reported in the composite literature.

6. COMPOSITE PARTS FABRICATION

6.1 Fabrication of flat panels

A thin panel with $[0]_8$ lay-up and a thick panel with $[0_2/45/0_2/45/0_2/45/0_2/45/0]_s$ lay-up were fabricated. In the making of the flat panels, we had the advantage of working with simple tool with which we did not encounter any fabrication difficulties. In the VARI set-up, a fill channel and a vent channel were incorporated to help fill, spread, and vent the resin (Fig 4a). Prior to resin infusion, entrained air bubbles of resin/hardener mixture was removed using the air-degassing unit (Fig 4b). Heat was used to reduce the resin viscosity through heating the resin pot and the mold plate in an oven maintained at 50°C . Upon reaching an equilibrium temperature, the degassed resin was infused through the fabrics. The composites were cured at 50°C for 6 hours plus free standing post-cured at 121°C for 4 hours and at 177°C for 4 hours.

Fig 4(a). VARI set-up for a flat panel

Fig 4(b). Degassing of resin

6.2 Fabrication of corrugated panels

Prior to actual part fabrication, numerical mold filling simulation was conducted using LIMS^[3] to evaluate the various injection strategies for the fabrication of the corrugated panel. As LIMS code was originally developed to handle only 2D-flow problems, effective in-plane fabric permeability was assumed in the flow analysis. The flow visualization plots for two simulations are presented in Fig 5(a)-(b). The optimum injection strategy was found to be a line-injection along one edge of the panel.

Fig 5(a). 2-points injection

Fig 5(b). Line-injection

In the fabrication of the corrugated panel, a single cloth orientation $[0^\circ]$ was adopted by aligning the warp of the carbon fabric in a direction parallel to the length of the part. In the fabric lay-up process, it was found that it was extremely difficult to drape the dry fabric to the contour shape of the mold. To enhance the draping and lay-up procedures, the carbon fabric originally coated with Kelvar tracer was subsequently replaced with one coated with glass tracer. The new carbon fabric was found to be softer in texture and was able to conform to the mold shape better.

In the VARI set-up (Fig 6.), a fill channel and a vent channel were incorporated to help fill, spread, and vent the resin. Prior to the infusion of resin, the mold/preform assembly was preheated to about 93°C in an oven for at least 1 hour while the resin pot was preheated to about 50°C in a separate oven for about 45 minutes. Throughout the infusion, gelation and curing stages, the mold/preform assembly was placed under vacuum within an oven maintained at 50°C .

A total of 3 corrugated panels of lay-up configurations: $[0]_8$, $[0]_{18}$ and $[0]_{23}$ were fabricated. The composites were cured at 50°C for 6 hours plus free standing post-cured at 121°C for 4 hours and at 177°C for 4 hours.

Fig 6. VARI set-up for the fabrication of corrugated panel

7. COMPOSITE PARTS EVALUATION

7.1 Flat panels

Fig 7 shows the cured thin and thick laminates. The ultrasonic C-scan images of the composite parts show complete fiber wetting. The wall thickness of the thin and thick laminates was measured to be about 2.5 – 2.6 mm and 7.4 – 7.6 mm respectively. The parts' thickness variation was attributed to nesting effect of the fabric layers. Two methods for determining the fiber volume fractions were adopted. These methods were the ignition loss of cured reinforced resins and the predictive calculation method. The ignition loss method was performed according to ASTM D2584 and the fiber volume fraction of the thin and thick laminates were found to be about 52% and 50% respectively. Using the predictive calculation for fiber volume determination (V_f is equal to the ply number multiplied by the areal weight divided by the part thickness and fiber density), the fiber volume fractions were estimated to be in the range of

48-51%. The agreement between ignition loss results and the predictive calculation was found to be good.

Fig 7. Thin and thick laminates with C-scan images

7.2 Corrugated panels

Fig 8(b) shows the thin corrugated panel made up of $[0]_8$ lay-up configuration. X-sectional examination of the composite part shows complete fiber wetting without apparent defect. Resin rich channels can be found on sections of the composite part coinciding with the bottom mold corners of the mold (Fig 8a). The measured part thickness of the flat sections ranges from 2.8-3.0 mm. Using the predictive calculation method, the fiber volume fraction based on flat

portions of the composite part was estimated to be about 43-46%.

Fig 8(a). Resin rich channels
at bottom mold corners

Fig 8(b). Thin corrugated panel

Fig 9a shows the thick corrugated panel with $[0]_{23}$ lay-up configuration. Despite an increase in the part thickness, X-sectional and optical micro-graphical examination (Fig 9b) of the composite part shows complete fiber wetting with no apparent defect. Resin rich channels (Fig 9a) can be found on the composite part sections coinciding with the bottom mold corners. The measured part thickness ranges from 7.5-7.9 mm. Using the predictive calculation method, the fiber volume fraction based on flat portions of the composite part was estimated to be about 46-49%. Using the acid-digestion test method, the fiber volume fraction was found to be about 45%.

Fig 9(a). Resin rich corners

Fig 9(b) Optical micro-graph (100x)

8. MECHANICAL EVALUATION

8.1 Tension & Compression properties

Standard test coupons for tension and compression tests were fabricated out of the thin laminate made using VARI process. The mechanical properties were obtained using an average of the results of five tests (Table 4) conducted using the Instron's Universal Testing Machine.

From Table 4, it is apparent that the tension properties (both stiffness and strength) of the VARI part is comparable to that of the prepreg/autoclave part. The compression properties of the VARI part, however, is relatively less superior. In particular, the compression strength of the VARI part is estimated to have 70% of the value of the prepreg/autoclave part.. For VARI components to be used as high performance components for aerospace application, extreme attention is necessary to look at compressive performance requirement. Nevertheless, the overall mechanical performance of the VARI part is deemed attractive, considering the differences in fabrication method.

Table 4: Mechanical properties comparison of carbon/epoxy composites made using VARI and prepreg/autoclave

Properties	433K/Resinufusion 8607™	6376-905-36%
Tensile modulus, E11t (GPa)	65	63
Compression, E11c (GPa)	48.7	56.7
Tension, E22t (GPa)	55	67.6
Compression, E22c (GPa)	47.2	51.8
Ultimate Tensile, U11t (MPa)	780.98	601
Ultimate Compression, U11c (MPa)	623	758
Ultimate Tensile, U22t (MPa)	717.15	777
Ultimate Compression, U22t (MPa)	507	738
Flexural Strength, Fs (MPa)	NA	1050
Flexural Modulus, Fm (MPa)	NA	59

8.2 Evaluation of corrugated panels

The flexural performances of corrugated panels of similar thickness ($\approx 6.3\text{mm}$) but made using different fabrication processes (VARI, RTM and prepreg/autoclave) were evaluated in terms of flexural stiffness and strength. It is interesting to note that the VARI part (433K/Resinufusion 8607 carbon/epoxy) exhibit similar stiffness but better strength than the RTM part (G924/Q6065 carbon/vinylester) probably because of better compressive matrix properties; and is less superior than that of the prepreg/autoclave part (6376C-905-36% carbon/epoxy). The stiffness and flexural strength of the VARI part is estimated to be 70-75% of that of the prepreg/autoclave part.

Fig 10. Flexural testing of corrugated panels

9. DISCUSSION

9.1 Limitation of VARI

In VARI, the mold consists of a single-sided hard tool with the opposing side of the tool consisting of vacuum-bagging material. The process creates the final mold cavity under vacuum with the part thickness determined by the amount of fabric compaction achieved by the available vacuum.

In the fabrication of flat panels, a simple flat mold was used. The mold cavity thickness variation under vacuum is in its minimal. The VARI process produces 2.5-2.6 mm thin (8-ply) and 7.4-7.6 mm (23 plies) thick laminates. For both laminates, the thickness per ply was estimated to be about 0.32mm, which corresponds to a fiber volume fraction (V_f) of about 50%. Apparently, with the limitation of vacuum integrity and compaction loss during the wet-out stage in VARI, it is very difficult for the process to make composite parts with fiber volume fraction as high as 60%.

In the fabrication of the corrugated panels, a complicated mold with corners was used. The mold cavity thickness under vacuum was significantly affected by the presence of corners and was not being uniform in all sections of the molds (The mold curvature effect on permeability and mold filling in liquid infusion process is discussed in detail by S.Bickerton et al.^[4-5]). In particular, composite sections at the top mold corners have "thinning" effect (high compaction results in high fiber volume fraction) while the sections at the bottom mold corners have resin rich channels (low compaction results in low fiber volume fraction).

Thus, in the absence of a rigid close mold and in the presence of corners, the part dimensional integrity of the composite parts made using VARI can be sacrificed. VARI is therefore deemed only for simple shape and part fabrication.

10. CONCLUSIONS

This work demonstrated the VARI process using high performance Resinfusion™ 8607R/H epoxy system to make composite parts of simple flat shape and complex corrugated contour. Carbon fiber reinforced parts with fiber volume fractions of 46-54% were produced.

Mechanical test carried out on standard coupons and corrugated panels suggest that the compression properties of composites which are matrix dominant are more sensitive to the fabrication method. In the VARI process, it is the limitation of vacuum integrity and compaction loss during the wet-out stage which make it difficult to achieve parts of equivalent qualities to that of the prepreg/autoclave part (prepreg are subjected to much higher compaction pressure using autoclave processing method).

In conclusion, VARI is deemed a promising low-cost composite fabrication technique for large and simple shape fabrication, e.g. composite wing skin, composite hull, sandwich panel etc. By taking advantage of the VARI process and using raw fiber and high temperature resin systems, users are able to move into the higher regimes of the aerospace industry with a very flexible and cost advantaged processing method.

11. REFERENCES

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